

Assessment of Family Structure on Attitude of Adolescents for National Security: A Case Study of Abuja Municipal Area Council

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Abstract

It is believed that the family is the cradle of peace and security in any society. The level of peace and security families enjoy reflects the peace and security of the Nation. This study, therefore, aimed at finding out how family structure affects the attitude of adolescents to National security in Abuja Municipal Area Council of Nigeria. A Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The target population was adolescents attending public senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. An Instrument titled "Attitude to National Security Scale" (ANSS) was used for data collection. The Instrument adapted from Sanyal's (2015) "Attitude Towards Terrorism and Political Violence Scale" was revalidated using Cronbach Alpha statistical tool and a reliability coefficient of 0.72 was obtained. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics while the hypotheses were tested using Chi-square statistical tool. The results show no significant difference in the attitude of adolescents towards peace and security across family structures. There was also no significant difference in the attitude of adolescents to National security based on gender. Majority of the participants showed positive attitudes towards National peace and security. The findings were discussed and it was recommended that Counsellors should build on the already existing positive attitudes of adolescents towards National security. Suggestions were made on how to enhance better attitude and subsequent actions among Nigerian youths and adolescents, towards the peace and security of the society.

Keywords: Family structure, Attitude, Adolescents, National Security

Introduction

The family has been given various definitions by various Psychologists and Sociologists. The term as well as the common family structure types has also been redefined based on the changing realities of the current times. Some current definitions of the family include: "People related by marriage, birth, consanguinity or legal adoption, who share a common kitchen and financial resources on a regular basis" (Sharma, 2013). Health Resources and Services Administration (HRSA, 2022) also defined it as "A unit of two or more persons united by marriage, blood, adoption, or consensual union, in general consulting a single household, interacting and communicating with each other. The family of man, woman and child is the basic building block of human society. Family is the most definitive part of who we are, and no society has ever successfully done without, replaced, or improved upon the family as the fundamental unit of human relatedness (Saunders, 1999). Life starts in the family and all other known human institutions are extension of the family. Thus, the history of family remains an unexplainable fact globally. (Sharma, 2013).

Anderson, (2014) sees "Family structure" as a term that describes the members of a household who are linked by marriage or bloodline and is typically used in reference to at least one child residing in the home under the age of 18. Some types of family structures include two-parent, one-parent, and "living with neither parent" (adoptive families, grandparent families or other relatives, foster care families or institutionalized children). However, since the mid-1940s other changes in family life have resulted in more complicated designations of family structure, including blended families, single-parent plus partner families (cohabiting couples, both opposite sex and same sex), multigenerational families, and binuclear families). Families can also be classified into several different dimensions, for example, by marriage type (monogamous, polygamous), by location (patrilocal, matrilocal, and avunculocal), authority (patriarchy, matriarchy), and by kin composition (nuclear, joint).

Attitude is defined as "the relatively stable overt behavior of a person which affects his status." It refers to verbal responses, opinion, habits, vegetative processes, tendencies to act, impulses to act, inhibitive impulses, feelings, wishes, values, motor sets, and various combinations of these. In Psychology, attitude is a psychological construct that is a mental and emotional entity that inheres or characterizes a person, their attitude or approach to something, or their personal view on it. Attitude involves their mindset, outlook and feelings. Attitudes are complex and are an acquired state through life experience. Attitude is an individual's predisposed state of mind regarding a value and it is precipitated through a responsive expression

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towards oneself, a person, place, thing, or even the attitude object which in turn influences the individual's thought and action. Most simply understood attitudes in psychology are the feelings individuals have about themselves and the world. (Ihuoma, 2018). Attitudes can be formed from a person's past and present. Some one's attitude is his status-fixing behavior. An attitude can be a positive or negative evaluation of people, objects, events, activities, and ideas. These evaluations determine how the individual will behave towards the particular object. Hence attitude towards national security is predicated on how people view, regard and act towards security matters. Attitudes which are common to a group are called social attitudes or "values". Investigation of attitudes depends upon the observation, quantification, and generalization of overt behavior. The best sources are indirect evidences of overt behavior.

Adolescence is expressed as the time or era following the starting or onset of puberty during which an individual develops from a child into an adult. Adolescence can still be described as the transitional period from childhood to adulthood ranging from 13-19 years of age. This period is characterized by lots of stress and storm and they can easily yield to peer and other pressures around them. Since most adolescents are still under the guardianship of their parents, it is obvious that the kind of home environment they come from will definitely affect how they navigate this all-important stage of their lives. Children that are raised from a peaceful and healthy family environment will grow with such healthy and peaceful attitude to the society at large. A dysfunctional family will raise unhealthy children that will in turn exhibit attitudes that affect the security of the nation (Chetty, Hendren, Kline, and Saez, 2014).

Ita (2011), described security as a situation where persons or groups are guarded from act of fears, uncertainty, anxiety and other disruptive tendencies. Merriam Webster Collegiate Dictionary (2020) defines it as the quality or state of being secure: such as freedom from danger (safety) and freedom from fear or anxiety. Gee (2016), opined that security is a situation where persons, group of persons, institution or government are guarded from the fear of the unknown, uncertainty or anxiety. Security therefore means a state of being safe or protected from harm, safety, as well as the measures taken to be safe or protected. It is a total peaceful condition of mindset of one, groups, states, institutions and nations at a particular period of time (Nmom, 2013).

Fundamentally, security has to do with the presence of peace, safety, gladness and the protection of human and physical resources or absence of crisis or threats to human dignity, all of which facilitate development and progress of any human society. On the other hand, the Merriam Webster Dictionary, defines insecurity as not being safe or protected'. It is the state of being open to danger, threat or injury. It is the anxiety that is experienced when one feels vulnerable and insecure. Ezemonye (2011) and the British House of Commons, (2015) affirms the above definition of insecurity as connoting the absence of peace, a state of rancour and being unsure of the present and of the future. Insecurity is rife in Nigeria. The dimensions include terrorism, kidnapping, Herders-Farmers crisis, cultism, rape, ritual killings and gangsterism, among others (Duerksen, 2021).

The family plays the most important role with regards to national security. Every nation depends primarily on the family for peace, security and development because children raised from a peaceful and healthy family environment will grow with such healthy and peaceful attitude to the society at large. A dysfunctional family will raise unhealthy children that will in turn exhibit attitudes that affect the security of the nation. The attitudes cultivated by these children will be what they will grow with. If children cultivate healthy and peaceful attitudes, so shall they exhibit in the larger society as opined by Ihuoma, (2008), Chetty et al, (2014) and Edwards, (2014).

In recent times, the family and world at large have been facing the worst level of security challenge far beyond the ability of the government to handle, and enhancing a pauperization of the family as an institution. In this vein, it is believed that there is a missing link to the problem of security; and that link is the family structure and relationship which is the foundation and starting point of demystifying the security problem in the nation. Historically, family structure in Nigeria has changed. These notable changes are influenced by other changes in the population like fewer and later marriages, marriages of shorter duration, more divorce followed by re-partnering or remarriage, more nonmarital unions (cohabitation), more children born outside marriage, and more women employed outside the home even with very young children (Edwards, (2014). For example, since 1950 the number of children residing with a married couple has decreased from slightly over 90 percent to about 74 percent. Concomitantly, the number of both mother-only and father-only families increased during this period, with mother-only families being more prevalent. Moreover, of all children living in mother-only families, about half of the mothers had never married, and about 30 percent were with divorced mothers (Anderson, 2014).

Nmom, (2013) posited that the main duty of any nation is to provide a safe and secured environment, establish viable interactive conditions for citizens to go about their legitimate activities. Even Section 14 subsection 2 (b) of the constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria revealed that security and welfare of the people should be the paramount role of the government.

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Therefore, security is a function of a nation's development and portrays the country's image in the world as a good nation. But insecurity poses a great challenge to achieving this goal. Since the security of a nation is very important, we have to examine the position of the family structure in support of security of the nation. Edwards, (2014) expressed that the nuclear family is the ultimate and self-sufficient unit in which husbands and wives are in charge of their children's upbringing. When a child turns out to be good the parents are happy and praised. But when a child turns out to be bad, the parents are not happy, rather they are blamed as though the parents were totally responsible. Children are reassured when they know the limit to their behavior that the society is not merely a place of unexplored chaos. It is orderly, with boundaries and appropriate behaviours. Within those boundaries the family states what it wants and what it does not want. It adds to family security and cohesiveness (M. As we give so we receive. As you sow so shall you reap. This is the same in raising children by parents in the family. If we sow the seed of neglect, acrimony, discord, selfishness and others, they will bear their fruits and that might be a contributory factor to the level of insecurity we are facing in our nation today.

The theories relating to the topic are the Family systems and Human ecology theories. The Family systems theory identifies family as a living organism which focuses on boundaries, rules, expectations and behavior and enhance family to be balanced. Alteration in any part of the family will certainly affect the entire system including the behavior of the people that make up the family. Therefore, to have a balanced family system, there must exist interconnectivity among the various units. On the other hand, the Human ecology theory focused on the environment an individual finds himself in. That the environment has an influence on individual character or upbringing. This tells about the person's relationship with others and resources at the exposure of the person in relation to his needs. It further explains that when a person finds himself in another environment better than the previous that there is that likelihood the individual will change (influence the person's character, positively or negatively). Hence the duty of parents to guide adolescents against negative peer pressure.

Huda (2019), determined the family role in facing the prevalence of terrorist ideas among adolescents. Results obtained revealed that the most significant indicators of the prevalence of terrorist being a security threat- ideas among adolescents are provoking a fierce argument with family members who disagree with them and showing intolerance towards others. The study recommended raising awareness among parents about the developmental characteristics, behavioral problems, and social and psychological pressures of various age-stages and preventing adolescents from watching porno movies. Alozie (2017), ex-rayed the impact of family structure on behavioural pattern of adolescents in Umuahia, Nigeria. The study made use of 650 families through stratified random sampling technique. Findings showed that maladaptive behaviours among adolescents from intact family are low when compared with non-intact families(single-parenting) which placed human society at great risk of insecurity. Furthermore, it recommended that husbands and wives endeavour to live together with their children so as to inculcate decent behaviours in them as a step towards reducing insecurity and its associated problems.

Nmom (2013), determined the role of family structure and attitudes of adolescents on national security. The findings showed that family security is much more relevant in national development including security. The study recommended family structure as the bedrock on which community security is footed. Pourkasamaei, Giliam, Nikanesh and Aghataghi (2013), studied on family structure and sense of security. The study utilized primary data in collection of data (questionnaire and oral interview) focused on males and females with age ranging from 15 years and above. The study revealed that traditional families have enjoyed more sense of security than democratic families and that men have higher positive attitude to security than women. This study therefore, examined the role of family structure in shaping the attitudes of adolescents in Abuja Municipal Area Council towards national security. Previous studies on the same or related topics dealt majorly on two family structures, (monogamous and polygamous) but this study is peculiar in its examination of other family structures like single parent and blended families and their roles in shaping adolescents' attitudes towards National security in Nigeria. The researcher is also not aware of similar studies being carried out in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Nigeria and other parts of the world are faced with security challenges. The existence of militia groups in Nigeria which include: Boko Haram, Islamic State in West Africa (ISWA), Niger Delta militants, Oduduwa People's Congress (OPC), Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), Bakassi group and others attest to this. The activities of these groups have resulted to death of many people, with millions inflicted with pains and injuries and property worth billions of Naira destroyed. There is also the menace of illegal violent protests, oil bunkering, kidnapping, street violence and cultism in schools, bomb blasts and others. The afore-mentioned groups and others turned to become security challenges facing the Nation-Nigeria, creating high level of fear among the people at individual, family, community, state and national levels.

Insecurity in Nigeria is linked with deteriorating and declining family values, broken homes, failed promises, failed expectations and hopelessness. According to Nmom (2013), the family has been in a confused state and security problems raging higher and higher on a daily basis. Since the political independence of Nigeria, on 1st October, 1960, Nigerian families

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has been described as families that exist only in name-where there is lack of unity among members and a decline in family value which affects the nation at large. This has resulted to calling the Nation-Nigeria, a failed State. Ita (2011), opined that families have failed to carry out their traditional roles as beacons of peace, security and development. Adolescents are raised with deviant behaviours, posing security threats at family and national levels. Additionally, polygamous families have been said to highlight higher levels of conflict, hostility, and aggression due to unbalanced treatment of wives by their husbands, financial anxiety and insecurity associated with supporting larger families and other family challenges such as full and half sibling rivalry and jealousy. Hence, a polygamous home environment appears to be less nurturing and more distressing to a child than a monogamous one. Intact families stand the chance to raise adolescents who will not turn to become security problem to the society. Traditionally too, it is believed that adolescents that received training under a single parent are likely to turn out badly in character than adolescents trained under both husbands and wives together. Therefore, it is believed that the primary problem of these adolescents is the structure of their individual families.

Having viewed the position of the family as the fundamental institution from which individuals primarily cultivate their character, it becomes obvious that the family plays a major role in security situation of a nation. This study therefore sought to find out how family structure affects the attitude of adolescents to National security in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to assess the effect of family structure on the attitudinal pattern of adolescents in Abuja Municipal Area Council towards national security. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine how adolescents from various family structures differ in their attitude towards national security
2. Determine the difference between male and female adolescents in their attitude towards national security
3. Assess attitude of adolescents from nuclear families and extended families towards national security

Research Questions

Based on the above objectives, the following research questions are formulated:

1. To what extent does family structure affect attitude of adolescents towards national security?
2. What is the extent to which male and female adolescents differ in their attitude regarding national security?
3. What is the extent to which attitude of adolescents from monogamous families differ from that of adolescents from extended families regarding national security?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between adolescents' attitude towards National security across their family structures.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female adolescents' attitude towards National security.
3. There is no significant difference between the attitudes of adolescents from nuclear and extended families towards National security.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was employed to generate data from the respondents. The target population comprised of adolescents attending public senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) of the Federal Capital Territory during the 2022/2023 session. The target population was about 12000 students in Senior secondary school classes 1 and 11. A sample of 120 adolescents representing 10% of the population were selected using random sampling technique. The sample consists of 35 male and 85 female adolescents aged 13–19 years. This age range was selected because they are at a very critical period of their lives and need to be guided towards making the right decisions in life. The study adopted a quantitative approach with a questionnaire titled “Attitude to National Security Scale (ANSS) used as the instrument for data collection. Questions were adapted from Sanyal’s (2015) “Attitude Towards Terrorism and Political Violence Scale”. The Instrument was revalidated by experts in Guidance and Counselling and Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was established using split-half method. The data was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha statistical tool with the reliability co-efficient of 0.72 which was considered high enough for the purpose of this study. The questionnaire was administered to respondents to generate information from them. The data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 16.0

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Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent to which male and female adolescents differ in their attitude regarding national security?

Table 1: Measures of students' attitudes towards national security across their family structure.

Family structure	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Monogamous	76	58.75	6.959
Polygamous	21	57.05	8.213
Single parent	12	56.67	6.443
Extended family	8	57.38	6.823
Blended family	3	64.00	5.292

(Field work, 2023)

Table 1 presents the measures of students' attitudes towards national security across their family structure. The table showed that the measure of attitude of those who are in blended family have the highest attitude. This is followed by monogamous family, then extended family, polygamous family and lastly the single parent family. Generally, however for all the participants, the average measures when compared with the maximum expected average measure of 80.0, their average measures were above average. This shows that adolescents, irrespective of their family structures are favourably disposed to National security.

Research Question 2

What is the difference between male and female adolescents in their attitude towards national security?

Table 2: Measures of male and female students' attitudes towards national security.

Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Male	35	58.63	7.685
Female	85	58.14	6.892

(Field work, 2023)

Table 2 presents the average measures of male and female students' attitudes towards national security. The table showed that the average male students' attitude towards national security (Mean = 58.63, Standard Deviation = 7.685) is higher than that of their female counterparts (Mean = 58.14, Standard Deviation = 6.892). Generally, however for both male and female participants, the average measures when compared with the maximum expected average measure of 80.0, their average measures were above average, showing that both male and female participants cherish national peace and security.

Research Question 3

How would the attitude of adolescents from nuclear families differ from that of adolescents from extended families towards national security?

Table 3: Measures of attitudes of adolescents from nuclear and extended families towards national security.

Family structure	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Nuclear family	76	58.75	6.959
Extended family	32	57.78	7.745

(Field work, 2023)

Table 3 presents the average measures of nuclear and extended families' attitudes towards national security. The table showed that the average measure of nuclear family's attitude towards national security (Mean = 58.75, Standard Deviation = 6.959) is higher than that of their extended family counterparts (Mean = 57.78, Standard Deviation = 7.745). Generally, however for both nuclear and extended families, the average measures when compared with the maximum expected average attitude measure of 80.0, their average measures were above average. This shows that adolescents from both nuclear and extended families desire peace and security in Nigeria.

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Hypothesis 1

There will be no significant difference between adolescents’ attitude towards National security across their family structures.

Table 4: Adolescents’ attitude towards National security across their family structures.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	187.392	3	62.464	1.246	0.296
Within Groups	5816.974	116	50.146		
Total	6004.367	119			

(Field work, 2023)

The F value of 1.246 in table 8 is not statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance, implying that the differences in the attitude measures of those from the five family types are not statistically significant and so cannot be generalized to the entire population. Hypothesis one is therefore accepted.

Table 5: Multiple Comparison of different family structure and how they were affected by national security.

(I)family structure	(j)family structure	Mean difference (i-j)	P-value
Monogamous	Polygamous	1.636	0.829
	Single parent	2.217	0.745
	Extended family	-3.916	0.697
Polygamous	Monogamous	-1.636	0.829
	Single parent	0.581	0.996
	Extended family	-5.552	0.481
Single parent	Monogamous	-2.217	0.745
	Polygamous	-0.581	0.996
	Extended family	-6.133	0.425
Extended family	Monogamous	3.916	0.697
	Polygamous	5.552	0.481
	Single parent	6.133	0.425

A further attempt was also made to locate the direction of differences with the aid of Scheffe post-hoc analysis. From Table 5, the mean comparison showed that differences exist between attitude measures of different family types sampled for the study, though the differences are not statistically significant and as such not generalizable. Table 5 above showed that extended family type had the highest average measure of attitude towards national security, followed by the monogamous family, which is followed by polygamous family. The single parent group had the lowest measure of attitude towards national security. The differences however are not statistically significant and as such cannot be generalized; it must have occurred due to sampling error. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between male and female students’ attitude towards National security.

Table 6: T-Test Analysis of the difference between male and female students’ attitude towards National security.

Sex	N	Mean	Std. D.	T	df	Sig.(2tailed)	Remark
Male	35	58.63	7.685	.340	118	.734	Ns
Female	85	58.14	6.892				

Table 6 presents the t-test comparison of difference between male and female students’ attitude towards National security. The t-test comparison showed that the difference in male and female adolescents’ average attitude was not statistically significant. This is evident from the sig-2 tailed values that is greater than the 0.05 benchmark. Since any t-test comparison of means of two groups which is greater than the 0.05 benchmark signifies insignificant difference in influence of the two groups (male and female adolescents), it therefore follows that the difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between male and female students’ attitude towards National security is accepted. The values of the mean average attitudes of male and female adolescents showed that the average attitude

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of male adolescents is higher than that of their female counterparts. Since the difference is not statistically significant, it cannot be generalized; it must have occurred due to sampling error. The hypothesis is also accepted.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between attitudes of adolescents from nuclear and extended families towards National security.

Table 7: Attitudes of adolescents from nuclear and extended families towards National security.

Family structure	N	Mean	Std. Dev	t	df.	Sig.(2tailed)	Remark
Nuclear	76	58.75	6.959	.639	106	.524	NS
Extended	32	57.78	7.745				

Table 7 presents the t-test comparison of difference between nuclear and extended families' average attitude towards National security. The t-test comparison showed that the difference in average attitude of nuclear and extended family adolescents was not statistically significant. This is evident from the sig-2 tailed values that is greater than the 0.05 benchmark. Since any t-test comparison of means of two groups which is greater than the 0.05 benchmark signifies insignificant difference in influence of the two groups (nuclear and extended family adolescents), it therefore follows that the difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between attitudes of adolescents from nuclear and extended families towards National security is accepted. The values of the mean average attitudes of adolescents from nuclear and extended families towards National security showed that the average attitude of adolescents from nuclear families is higher than that of their counterparts who are adolescents from extended families. Since the difference is not statistically significant, it cannot be generalized; it must have occurred due to sampling error.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one and hypothesis one looked at the role family structure plays in shaping the attitude of adolescents towards national security. The null hypothesis was accepted signifying that there was no difference in the attitude of adolescents in Abuja Municipal Area Council towards national security across the family structures. All the adolescents scored above average showing a favourable disposition to peace and tranquility in the nation, irrespective of their family structures. This could mean that families are eschewing internal rivalries and presenting a common front in fighting insecurity in Nigeria. This is a good omen for the nation. Since the families are united in their attitudes against insecurity, in no distant time, security challenges will become a thing of the past in Nigeria. Since adolescents are not favourably disposed to insecurity, recruiting them to various terrorist groups will become impossible and the groups will gradually fizzle out. This is in consonance with the work of Nmomo (2013), who opined that the family is the bedrock of National security. Families at peace means a Nation at peace. Moreso, the activities of the various terrorist groups have kept every Nigerian worried particularly those in Northern Nigeria. Almost every Nigerian knows the feeling of insecurity, family structure notwithstanding. Some have experienced it themselves while some have family members, neighbours, friends and relations who have been victims of these attacks and everybody desires an end to such activities irrespective of what is happening at home.

The results of research question two and hypothesis two also revealed that there is no significant difference in the attitude of adolescents to national security based on gender. That signifies that both male and female adolescents are highly positive towards national security and peace. Again, the incessant security issues and experiences might be responsible for this stance. Insurgency and insecurity is not gender bound. Everybody suffers it. This is in accord with the findings of Nmomo (2013) who views peace and security as involving all people and groups without discrimination. However, this result is contrary to the findings of Pourkasamaei, Giliam, Nikanesh and Aghataghi (2013) who discovered that males have more positive attitude towards security than females.

The third research question and hypothesis which stated that there will be no significant difference between the attitudes of adolescents from nuclear and extended families towards National security was accepted. This means that family structure does not really affect student's attitude towards national security. It could be seen that adolescents irrespective of their family structure seek peace and security for the nation. Everyone is appalled by the experiences of victims of insecurity and would want an end to it. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Nmomo (2013), who sees security as a total peaceful condition of mindset of one, groups, states, institutions and nations without any difference in group. However, Alozie, (2017) is of a negative opinion as he posits that maladaptive behaviours among adolescents from intact families are low when compared

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with those from non-intact families. Anderson, (2014), also posited that children raised in Nuclear families possess more adaptive behaviours than those raised in other family structures.

Implications for Counselling

The findings of this study show that adolescents from various family structures have positive attitudes towards National security. Majority of them expressed the opinion that insecurity does the nation no good and that perpetrators should be brought to book. Counsellors are to leverage on this positive attitude and build a strong character of peace and security among adolescents irrespective of their family structures (Haruna & Gurjiya, 2022), knowing fully well that peaceful homes will equate a peaceful society.

Conclusion

The study showed that adolescents in AMAC view insecurity in Nigeria negatively, family structure and gender notwithstanding. This shows that everyone is feeling the impact of the negative activities of terrorists, insurgents, kidnapers and others in the Nation. Adolescents from various family structures want an end to insecurity in Nigeria. With this united front of various family structures, the end of insecurity in Nigeria is very much in sight. We have more uniting us than dividing us.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of positive attitude of adolescents towards national security, the following recommendations are made:

1. Governments should organize more sensitization and advocacy programmes on National security and peace for adolescents, including those in rural areas.
2. More sensitization programmes should also be targeted at families and communities, emphasizing on the things that unite us as against the things that divide us.
3. Counsellors should build on the already positive attitudes of adolescents towards ensuring peaceful co-existence of the citizens of Nigeria.

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